

Appendix G: Comments on fitting issues

AzV 469, Figures I.1 and J.1. The fit quality of this star is very good. The only oddity is the shape of the core of $H\alpha$, which could be the result of wind contamination. It is unlikely that the morphology is the result of two components.

AzV 372, Figures I.2 and J.2. A problem in this fit is with the $He\text{I } \lambda 4922$, which is over-predicted in the model. This issue could be resolved by increasing the temperature or decreasing the helium mass fraction. However, this would ruin the fit to other helium lines.

AzV 456, Figures I.3 and J.3. The most glaring issue for this star is the morphology of $H\alpha$, which we were unable to replicate with our models.

AzV 327, Figures I.4 and J.4. The fit for this star is good in general, with no major issues. The SED of this star shows abnormally high fluxes in the FUSE range. This is due to a nearby, UV-bright object, the light of which was included in the large FUSE aperture.

AzV 235, Figures I.5 and J.5. We note one major discrepancy between the predicted and observed $Si\text{IV } \lambda 1394 - 1403$ P Cygni profile. Our estimated wind density parameters yield a satisfactory fit for other wind features. Our attempts to fit the silicon lines using models with clumpier winds had little effect on the fit of the silicon lines, but it lowered the quality of the fit for the other wind lines.

AzV 215, Figures I.6 and J.6. The line fits for this object are of high quality with no major issues.

AzV 104, Figures I.7 and J.7. The notable issue with this star is the fit for the absorption core of $H\alpha$. Attempting to remedy the discrepancy, we tried fitting this line with models that possess clumpier winds, which yielded better results, which made fitting the carbon P Cygni profile impossible.

AzV 410, Figures I.8 and J.8. The line fits of photospheric lines are satisfactory. The UV lines show a discrepancy between predictions and observations, specifically the silicon lines. The lines are predicted as strong P Cygni profiles with strong red-shifted emission, while they lack any emission features in the observations. In the SED fitting of this star, we make use of the HST COS G230LB archival observation to constrain the reddening law parameters.

AzV 242, Figures I.9 and J.9. The overall line fits for this object are satisfactory with no notable discrepancies.

AzV 96, Figures I.10 and J.10. The only issue in this fit is that the predicted blue-shifted absorption of $H\alpha$ is much narrower than the observed. Overall, the line fits are satisfactory.

AzV 264, Figures I.11 and J.11. Similar to AzV 96, the blue-shifted absorption of $H\alpha$ in the model is much narrower than in the observations.

AzV 175, Figures I.12 and J.12. Satisfactory fits for all lines with no notable discrepancies.

Sk 191, Figures I.13 and J.13. In $H\alpha$, there is a moderate, but significant velocity shift. In addition, the predicted $Si\text{IV } \lambda 1394 - 1403$ lines, which are seemingly photospheric, do not match the strong P Cygni observations. Finally, the red $He\text{I } \lambda 6678$ and $He\text{I } \lambda 7065$ lines are much broader than other helium lines, suggesting higher rotational broadening parameters are required to obtain a satisfactory fit. These issues all point towards this star being a potential binary.

AzV 18, Figures I.14 and J.14. Similar to AzV 96, the extremely broad blue-shifted absorption of the observed $H\alpha$ is not matched by the model.

NGC330-ELS-04, Figures I.15 and J.15. The observed line diagnostics are generally well reproduced, except for the absorption strength $H\alpha$. The small peak in the left wing of $H\alpha$ could be an artifact of normalisation.

AzV 187, Figures I.16 and J.16. The fit is generally satisfactory. Similar to NGC330-ELS-04, the absorption strength of $H\alpha$ is exaggerated in the model.

AzV 22, Figures I.17 and J.17. Overall satisfactory line fits. Although we do not employ the $O\text{I } \lambda 7772 - 7774 - 7775$ multiplet in obtaining the oxygen abundance for this object, we include it to show that fitting these lines would require a significantly lower oxygen abundance compared to fitting $O\text{II}$ lines.

AzV 393, Figures I.18 and J.18. This star is the sole hypergiant in our sample. We get satisfactory fits for most lines. The emission components in $H\alpha$ and $H\beta$ are well-matched by the model. However, we were unable to decrease the strength of the predicted absorption to match the observation without affecting the fits of other lines.

AzV 343, Figures I.19 and J.19. The quality of the fits in general is satisfactory. We note that for this star, due to the lack of $O\text{II}$ lines, we obtain the oxygen mass fraction by fitting the $O\text{I } \lambda 7772 - 7774 - 7775$ multiplet.

AzV 324, Figures I.20 and J.20. Similar to AzV 343, for the determination of the oxygen mass fraction, we resorted to fitting the $O\text{I } \lambda 7772 - 7774 - 7775$ multiplet. No major issues in the fits of this object, and the quality of the fits in general is satisfactory.

Appendix H: Spectral energy distribution (SED)

In Fig. [H.1](#) we present the SED fits for the entire sample.

Fig. H.1: Spectral energy distribution for all the stars in our sample. Red solid line: model SED, Black solid line: observed SED. The photometric points are indicated as blue circles.

Fig. H.1: continued

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Appendix I: Line fitting for individual stars

Fig. I.1-I.20 are the individual diagnostic line fits for each star in our sample. In each row, from top to bottom, the diagnostic lines are used to determine the effective temperature, the effective surface gravity, the wind density parameters (mass loss rate, β , clumping parameters), the helium abundance, the nitrogen abundance, the carbon abundance, and the oxygen abundance, respectively.

Fig. I.1: Individual line fits for AzV 469 (O9 Iab(f)). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.2: Individual line fits for AzV 372 (O9.2 Iab). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.3: Individual line fits for AzV 456 (O9.5 Iab). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.4: Individual line fits for AzV 327 (O9.7 Ib). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.5: Individual line fits for AzV 235 (B0 Ia). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.6: Individual line fits for AzV 215 (B0 Ia). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.7: Individual line fits for AzV 104 (B0.5 Ia). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.8: Individual line fits for AzV 410 (B0.7 Iab). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.9: Individual line fits for AzV 242 (B0.5 Ia). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.10: Individual line fits for AzV 96 (B1 Iab). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.11: Individual line fits for AzV 264 (B1 Ia). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.12: Individual line fits for AzV 175 (B1.5 Ib). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.13: Individual line fits for Sk 191 (B1.5 Ia). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.14: Individual line fits for AzV 18 (B2 Ia). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.15: Individual line fits for NGC330 ELS 04 (B2.5 Ib). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.16: Individual line fits for AzV 187 (B2.5 Ia). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.17: Individual line fits for AzV 22 (B3 Ia). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.18: Individual line fits for AzV 393 (B3 Ia⁺). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.19: Individual line fits for AzV 343 (B8 Iab). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Fig. I.20: Individual line fits for AzV 324 (B8 Ib). Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model.

Appendix J: Overall spectral fits

Fig. **J.1-J.20** are the fits for the overall spectrum of each star in our sample.

Fig. J.1: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 469 (O9 Iab(f)). From the top, the first panel displays the FUV FUSE range, which contains interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second panel is the STIS E140M FUV range. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.2: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 372 (O9.2 Iab). From the top, the first panel displays the FUV FUSE range, which contains interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.3: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 456 (O9.5 Iab). From the top, the first panel displays the FUV FUSE range, which contains interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.4: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 327 (O9.7 Ib). From the top, the first panel displays the FUV FUSE range, which contains interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second and third panels are COS G130M + Cos G160M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.5: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 235 (B0 Ia). From the top, the first panel displays the FUV FUSE range, which contains interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.6: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 215 (B0 Ia). From the top, the first panel displays the FUV FUSE range, which contains interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.7: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 104 (B0.5 Ia). From the top, the first panel displays the FUV FUSE range, which contains interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.8: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 410 (B0.7 Iab). From the top, the first and second panels are STIS E140M FUV and COS G230MLB UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.9: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 242 (B0.7 Ia). From the top, the first panel displays the FUV FUSE range, which contains interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.10: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 96 (B1 Iab). From the top, the first panel displays the FUV FUSE range, which contains interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.11: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 264 (B1 Ia). From the top, the first panel displays the FUV FUSE range, which contains interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.12: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 175 (B1.5 Ib). From the top, the first panel displays the FUV FUSE range, which contains interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second panel is the COS G130M + COS G160M FUV. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, $O\text{I} + P\text{II}$ λ 1302, $C\text{II}$ λ 1335, $Si\text{II}$ λ 1527, and $Al\text{II}$ λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines $Ca\text{II}$ H + K and $Na\text{I}$ D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.13: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk 191 (B1.5 Ia). From the top, the first panel displays the FUV FUSE range, which contains interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, $O\text{ I} + P\text{ II}$ λ 1302, $C\text{ II}$ λ 1335, $Si\text{ II}$ λ 1527, and $Al\text{ II}$ λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines $Ca\text{ II H} + K$ and $Na\text{ I D}$ are interstellar features.

Fig. J.14: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 18 (B2 Ia). From the top, the first panel displays the FUV FUSE range, which contains interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.15: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of NGC330 ELS 04 (B2.5 Ib). From the top, the first panel and second panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, $O\text{I} + P\text{II}$ λ 1302, $C\text{II}$ λ 1335, $Si\text{II}$ λ 1527, and $Al\text{II}$ λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines $Ca\text{II} H + K$ and $Na\text{I} D$ are interstellar features.

Fig. J.16: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 187 (B2.5 Ia). From the top, the first panel displays the FUV FUSE range, which contains interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second and third panels are COS G130M + COS G160M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.17: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 22 (B3 Ia). From the top, the first and second panels are the STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $L\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at \approx 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.18: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 393 (B3 Ia⁺). From the top, the first panel is the FUV FUSE range, containing interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second and third panels are COS G130M + COS G160M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. J.19: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 343 (B8 Iab). From the top, the first panel and second panels are COS G130M + COS G160M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, $O\text{I} + P\text{II}$ λ 1302, $C\text{II}$ λ 1335, $Si\text{II}$ λ 1527, and $Al\text{II}$ λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines $Ca\text{II} H + K$ and $Na\text{I} D$ are interstellar features.

Fig. J.20: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of AzV 324 (B8 Ib). From the top, the first and second panels are COS G130M + COS G160M FUV and STIS E230M UV, respectively. We note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.